

Baltic MUPPETS

**Baltic
MUPPETS**

DELIVERABLE 6.1

COMMUNICATION

STRATEGY

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Baltic MUPPETS is a three-year project funded by the Interregional Innovation Investment (I3) Instrument. The project aims to create a new value chain for small mussels (1-3 cm) from the Baltic Sea by developing high-value pet food products. Communication plays a fundamental role in the project; it contributes to creating a proper environment for the project's success.

The present document outlines the communication strategy developed for Baltic MUPPETS as part of the WP6 Communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results. The communication strategy has been designed to be a meaningful guide to ensure effective internal and external communication throughout the project to increase visibility and maximise the impact and uptake of results by key users and stakeholders.

Throughout the document, the role of the work package leader as well as that of the other project partners, is described. The latter allows all parties involved to be on the same ground and work collaboratively to transform the project's work into impact.

The project's communication strategy includes communication objectives, target audiences, key messages, communication channels, visual identity, and actions to be taken as part of the WP6. This document provides direction for content development efforts, as well as the communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the project and its results. It includes clear indicators to evaluate the communication progress and success throughout the project.

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ACRONYMS

BSR	Baltic Sea Region
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
I3	Interregional Innovation Investment Instrument
KER	Key Exploitable Result
M	Month
PC	Project Coordinator
PDEC	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities
PSG	Project Steering Group
PP	Project Partner(s)
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package

INTRODUCTION

Due to low salinity, Baltic Sea mussels are often smaller and, therefore, not always suitable for the human consumption market. In the western Baltic Sea, small mussels are considered a side-stream of market-size mussel production. Baltic MUPPETS is a three-year project funded under the Interregional Innovation Investment (I3) Instrument and aims to create a new value chain for small mussels in the Baltic Sea Region (BSR) by developing high-value and healthy pet food products.

The project will invest in innovative submerged farming, harvesting and processing technologies, contributing to local economic growth and quality employment opportunities. Besides the socioeconomic benefits, mussel farming will provide a range of ecosystem services such as nutrient removal, improved water quality, and increased biodiversity.

The following document defines the communication strategy for the project. It includes the communication objectives, target audiences, key messages, channels, visual identity and actions for the project that shall be implemented under WP6 Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results.

1. PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document shall provide meaningful guidance to ensure effective internal and external communication throughout the project to increase visibility and maximise the impact and uptake of results by key users and stakeholders.

The communication strategy is relevant to all work packages, as it defines the flow of information both between the partners themselves and with external stakeholders. It is expected to contribute to developing high-quality project communications materials, knowledge products and their dissemination. The strategy is designed to achieve impact among local and international stakeholder groups and across the quintuple helix of innovation (academia, industry, civil society, and government).

The timeline encompasses the entire three years of the project and continuing post-project to ensure the project's sustainability and that outputs are available for reuse and further development.

The implementation of the communication strategy will be further elaborated in the deliverable 6.2 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation (PDEC). The PDEC will be available in M5 (end of May 2023).

2. DEFINITIONS AND TERMINOLOGY

- Communication^{1,2}: any activity that promotes the project, its actions and results, providing targeted and factually accurate information to different audiences. The activities must be effective, proportionate, strategic and coherent, and whenever possible and appropriate, foster a two-way exchange. Communication starts at the outset of the project and carries on throughout.
- Community of Practice (CoP): a group of key stakeholders who share a common concern, a set of problems, or an interest.
- Dissemination^{1,2}: any activity that makes the project's results available for others to use. It happens once results are available and often targets specialist audiences.
- Exploitation^{1,2}: any activity that makes concrete use of the project's results, once available. It enables the uptake and the use of the results and targets specialist audiences. It covers the result phase of the project and beyond.
- Impact³: intended or unintended long-term effect of activities using the resources of a project or the work performed therein.
- Key Exploitable Result (KER): an identified main result (output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information) which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits-downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an essential input to policy, further research or education. Prioritisation of the result should be derived from evaluating the following criteria: degree of innovation, exploitability and impact.
- Knowledge transfer: sharing knowledge, abilities and ideas across one organisation. It seeks to organise, create, capture or distribute knowledge and ensure its availability for future users.
- Outcome³: the project's short- or long-term effects stemming from the stakeholder uptake or interaction with the project's outputs.
- Output³: immediate direct results of the project
- Stakeholder³: an individual or community interested in or concerned about the project or its impacts.

3. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

Stakeholder mapping is a method to identify and understand the people or groups with an interest or influence on a particular project, organisation, or decision. It involves creating a visual representation, often in the form of a chart or diagram, that shows the stakeholders, their interests or concerns, and their power or influence.

The purpose of stakeholder mapping is to help prioritise the actions and communication efforts based on each stakeholder's level of importance and influence. It can also help ensure stakeholders' needs and expectations are considered when making decisions.

When creating the stakeholder map, the PP first identified all the stakeholders involved in or concerned with the Baltic MUPPETS project in a workshop. In the second step, their interests, needs, concerns, expectations, and level of power or influence were analysed and visualised. The mapping was based on former projects, the existing SUBMARINER Network stakeholder database, PP input, and desk research.

Based on this analysis, the stakeholders were categorised into groups to determine the best way to engage with each group and tailor the communication activities accordingly:

A. High influence, interested stakeholder: Key stakeholders

These are the project's key stakeholders to achieve the project objectives, and therefore they should be engaged closely and regularly.

B. High influence, less interested stakeholder: Mid-level stakeholders

The mid-level stakeholders should be kept satisfied, but the intensity of communication actions should not be too high that they become bored. They can be facilitators at a time; others might follow contradicting interests and negatively use their influence and put the project's objectives at risk.

C. Low influence, interested people: Low-level stakeholders

The low-level stakeholders should be informed and heard to ensure no significant issues arise. The project can profit enormously from these stakeholders being multipliers.

D. Low influence, less interested people: Monitored stakeholders

These potentially interested stakeholders should be monitored but not overloaded with excessive communication.

Figure 1 Stakeholder Mapping

Communication and dissemination activities target all identified groups with varying and well-defined goals. Activities and means are chosen following those goals and can be divided into Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation activities. It is crucial to enter dialogues with potential facilitators and risk groups to ensure the highest level of support and to avoid the opposition of actors who either strongly influence the positive outcome of or are affected by the project outputs. Formats for engagement are selected following the specific purposes and objectives of engaging with the members of the respective groups. Forms for communication are described in the following sections and further elaborated in the CDEP.

An initial baseline stakeholder database will be compiled by M3 of the project, using SUBMARINER Network’s extensive stakeholder database accumulated over 15 years of European projects in the blue economy. Additional stakeholders will be added to this list throughout the project, with contributions from project partners, specifying which KER(s) is/are most relevant to that stakeholder.

4. KEY MESSAGES

4.1 Mission Statement

A mission statement communicates the purpose of the project. It is a concise and straightforward statement defining the project's intent.

The Baltic MUPPETS project aims to establish regenerative mussel production in the Baltic, contributing to local economic growth while providing a range of ecosystem services such as nutrient removal, improved water quality, and increased biodiversity.

4.2 Tagline

The tagline is a short, easily remembered phrase to identify the project quickly. It is often used in association with the logo.

Baltic MUPPETS - Mussels for pet food, a viable business beneficial to the environment

Baltic MUPPETS: Small mussels with great value

4.3 Boilerplate

A boilerplate text can be reused in multiple documents without significant changes to the original. The text should be used whenever the project needs to be concisely presented (policy briefs, blog articles, press releases, job advertisements, etc.). Therefore, it should only include the essential details of the project and its objectives.

Baltic MUPPETS is a three-year project funded under the Interregional Innovation Investment (I3) Instrument. It aims to create a new value chain for small mussels in the Baltic Sea region by developing high-value and healthy pet food products. The project will invest in innovative submerged farming, harvesting and processing techniques, contributing to local economic growth and quality employment opportunities. Besides the socioeconomic benefits, mussel farming will provide a range of ecosystem services such as nutrient removal, improved water quality, and increased biodiversity.

4.4 Key Messages for Specific Stakeholder Groups

Stakeholder Group	Objective	Message
Key stakeholders	Promote the concept of mussel farming in the Baltic Sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is an economic potential for small mussels from the Baltic Sea - Translating new knowledge and innovative products into business opportunities - Strengthening European mussel cultivation and processing sectors
Multipliers	Improve the existing knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key messages from the key exploitable results (KERs)
Facilitators or risks	Enable decision takers to take more informed decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mussel production when planned wisely represents a great nature-based solution to fight eutrophication - By using new technologies, mussel farming can create attractive employment opportunities - Innovative submerged farming techniques improve social acceptance
Potentially interested parties	Raise awareness on positive effects of mussel farming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible consumption: mussel cultivation is a climate friendly production of marine proteins - Supporting sustainable and local production

Table 1 Key Messages for Specific Stakeholder Groups

5. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES AND TOOLS

5.1 Internal Communication

5.1.1 Communication platform

As an internal communication platform, Microsoft (MS) Teams was chosen due to several reasons:

- MS Teams is included in the office package.
- External users (PP) can access as guests.
- Data is accessible on all devices, including mobile phones.
- Many possibilities included in MS Teams like virtual meetings, exchange of documents, chat function and internal calendar to keep track of tasks and deliverables.

The main advantage of Teams for the BALTIC MUPPETS project is the possibility to share results and internal documents. Therefore, all PP can upload and download documents via SharePoint in an organised and structured way.

Several channels exist for a better structure in MS Teams for the project, as shown in figure 2. Each channel consists of a chat function for questions, small discussions, shared information or invitations for upcoming meetings. To maintain the chat function in the single channel structured, it is possible to give a new message a title and reply directly to this message.

Channels can be set on a private mode with only specific persons allowing access in case documents filed under this channel should not be shared publicly.

Figure 2 Internal MS Teams communication channels

5.1.2 Meetings

5.1.2.1 Project partner meetings

The Baltic MUPPETS project partner meetings occur once a year in person, eventually in hybrid formats, to allow broad participation. Thus, the project will hold at least three partner meetings for the duration of the project. The meeting's date, location and hosting partner are always determined at least two months before the event. The partner meetings will be combined with other events or significant conferences, such as the on-site visits to the mussel farms, to maximise the project's impact and make travel efficient.

5.1.2.2 WP meetings

Apart from the physical all-partner meetings, regular conference calls for each work package will be set up to continually assess the progress of all tasks and risk management, brainstorming and planning of the next steps. The organisation and frequency of these meetings lie in the responsibility of each WP lead.

5.1.2.3 PSG meetings

Meetings of the Project Steering Group (PSG) will take place on a monthly or at least a bi-monthly basis; should critical events or situations arise, these will be shifted to bi-weekly until any issues are effectively resolved, then returning to month or bi-monthly depending on require input and the rotating agenda. The Coordinator leads such PSG meetings. The Coordinator and the leads of the different WPs are part of the PSG.

These meetings enable the overall management of the WPs. Additionally, risks and raised issues can be discussed, as well as connections and dependencies between single tasks of the different WPs.

5.1.2.4 General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is the decision-making body of the consortium and shall consist of one representative of each PP. The GA is chaired by the Coordinator, who will convene ordinary meetings at least once every six months and extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request by any PP.

The written notice of an ordinary meeting needs to be sent to the PP at least 14 days before and seven days before an extraordinary meeting.

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the PP must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any PP may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all other PPs by seven calendar days preceding the ordinary meeting and two days preceding an extraordinary meeting. Meetings of the General Assembly may be held in person or by tele- or videoconference or other telecommunication means.

5.2 External Communication

5.2.1 Project Website

The Baltic MUPPETS website (www.balticmuppets.eu) is the central communication platform of the project, as it provides access to general and specific information on the project, its progress and the partners involved. It will be regularly updated and supplied with new content, such as news items or recent publications.

The website showcases the three mussel farms, informs on mussel cultivation in the Baltic Sea region, the different work packages and provides information on the cascade funding/open calls. It also includes a section dedicated to all project-related publications: newsletters, deliverables, and scientific manuscripts.

The website content should refrain from using specific jargon that can be difficult to grasp for non-specialist audiences. The website will remain online for at least two years after the project ends.

A QR code directing to the project website is available to the PP to include in their presentations and other communications.

PP wishing to add content to the website should contact the WP lead.

All PP are requested to include a link to the project website on their institution/company website where possible.

Indicators:

Google Analytics is used to monitor the following indicators:

- unique visitors/month: 50 by month 12 – 100 by month 18
- total number of visits/month
- page views
- time spent/visit
- page views/visit

5.2.2 Social Media

Baltic MUPPETS will be active on two social media platforms: LinkedIn and Twitter. These are used to communicate easily and quickly with a broad audience to share short news and announcements. Social media is also a tool to foster engagement and discussions and to increase expertise recognition.

For Twitter, a list of relevant accounts to follow and handles and hashtags to use will be set up and shared via the project's MS Teams folder.

Some content will be planned for yearly special dates, e.g. world ocean day, and other content will be produced on an ad-hoc basis (e.g. participation at conferences).

A calendar with special dates and events will be created to prepare planned events.

An MS Teams Channel will be set up to gather tweets from PP to be published.

All PP are requested to follow the project's social media and share the links in their networks. The PP should retweet/share the project's posts as much as possible.

Redacted tweets will be communicated to the PPs for important announcements to facilitate sharing.

As individuals, PPs are encouraged to share the project's posts with personal profiles.

Indicators:

- number of followers: 300 minimum
- number of retweets/sharing and likes
- number of posts

5.2.3 Promotion Material

The promotion materials that will be developed for Baltic MUPPETS entail the following:

- flyers
- posters
- roll-up banner
- project summary/factsheet

Initially, the flyers, posters and factsheets will give a general overview of the Baltic MUPPETS project. Throughout the implementation of the project, the leaflets and factsheets will be updated depending on the target audiences, the stages and the progress made. Another poster will be created at the mid-term of the project to highlight the outcomes and future outcomes.

The roll-up banner contains a QR code leading to the Baltic MUPPETS website and will not be revised.

The PP should distribute the flyers, posters and factsheets at relevant events and through their networks to raise awareness of the project and its expected impacts.

Additional materials can be developed upon request depending on budget and personnel availability. A minimum of three weeks is required for the preparation of such materials.

Materials can be produced in other languages, provided that the requesting party supplies the corresponding translated texts.

5.2.4 Slide Templates

The slide template is a homogeneous set that follows the Baltic MUPPETS visual identity for dissemination slideshows.

The Baltic MUPPETS available slide deck is a collection of approximately 15 slides summarising the project's structure, objectives and expected impacts.

A reduced version of 3 slides is also available.

To ensure consistency throughout the duration of the project, all presentations promoting the project should be based on the slide templates.

The contents of the presentations shall be tailored to the target audience.

Similarly, the slide deck prepared to this effect should be used when giving a generalist overview of the project.

Partners are asked to provide a copy of any presentation held on behalf of the project.

5.2.5 Videos

Videos to present the project and its key results will be produced. They will be published on the project website and promoted through social media accounts.

PP are encouraged to share the videos in their networks and with the Press Relations department of their institutions.

Indicators:

- Number of views: 500 by the end of the project

5.2.6 Newsletter

At least three newsletters will be published to broadly inform external stakeholders of the project's progress and related events. The information will include critical announcements such as webinars, workshops, and publication of documents, including scientific and policy-related news in an easy-to-read format.

The newsletter will be published on the project website, and a subscription is possible, so interested parties will receive the newsletter by email. It will also be promoted through social media channels from the SUBMARINER Network and the PP.

The information to feed the newsletter will be collected regularly from the PP.

News from the Baltic MUPPETS project will also be published in the newsletter of the SUBMARINER Network with currently 6,000 subscribers.

Indicators:

- Number of subscribers
 - 300 minimum by the end of the project
 - 100 by month 12 – 150 by month 18 – 200 by month 24
- Number of unsubscribers

5.2.7 Press releases and blog articles

Press releases and blog articles will be published on the website and promoted on social media channels. Mainly, press releases will be distributed to the relevant amplifiers, such as media contacts, networks, other projects and businesses.

Blog articles will focus on specific topics and be written with a personal perspective. They could also take the shape of a longer featured interview with a PP or a stakeholder.

A list of topics to be covered will be established together with the PP. Information on the progress and evolution will be collected through the internal meetings, particularly the monthly project steering group meetings, and the milestones and deliverables.

PP wishing to promote specific topics can contact the WP lead for this request. They are also encouraged to initiate the process and ask for support from WP6.

5.2.8 Events

A variety of stakeholder-specific events will be organised throughout the project:

- four business events focused on marketing strategies of innovative Baltic MUPPETS products, e.g. open innovation events, pitching and match-making sessions,
- three on-site visits at the mussel farms,
- meetings of the Working Groups/Communities of Practice,
- and a final conference.

An event preparation toolkit will be developed and available in the project's MS Teams folder. It contains a sign-up sheet, the informed declaration of consent for participants to sign and an event reporting form to collect specific information post-event to feed the project's website and social media. This general toolkit can be completed with the project's available flyer and dedicated, more specific booklet if necessary. These must be requested in advance for design and review time (ca. three weeks).

All toolkit documents will be designed with the Baltic MUPPETS visual identity and layout.

The PPs are expected to participate in events and present the project with stands and presentations at conferences and workshops. It is strongly advised that the PPs inform the CO in advance, ideally as soon as the PPs are informed of the nature of their contribution, as this would allow the preparation of outreach campaigns online and onsite (e.g., booth, poster).

Indicators:

- Number of participants

5.2.9 Communities of Practice (CoP)

A community of practice (CoP) is a group of individuals who share a common interest or area of expertise and engage in regular communication and collaboration to improve their knowledge and skills. The establishment of a CoP will increase the probability of adequate uptake and exploitation of the project activities and outputs and make use of synergies with other projects and stakeholders.

The establishment and involvement of the CoP will be organised through Working Groups and an Online Community Platform.

The CoP work will be divided into different Working Groups, each covering an essential thematic topic and having its own activities and meetings.

The central Working Group is the SUBMARINER Network Mussels Working Group, which holds regular online meetings every three months. Additionally, the existing Working Groups on Macro-Algae and Multi-Use, together with the Business Accelerator and Mentoring will be an integral part of the Baltic MUPPETS project.

To allow members of the CoPs to interact with one another, such as sharing information, exchanging ideas, providing feedback, and collaborating on projects outside of the online Working Group meetings, an online community platform will be set up.

Indicators:

- Number of participants in the Working Group meetings
- Number of registered profiles on the community platform

6. VISUAL IDENTITY

The purpose of the visual identity is to strengthen the recognizability of the project throughout all communication activities and materials.

A graphic designer (<https://iggyvisual.com/graphic-design/>) has developed a project logo, typography, and core colour palette. The project logo will be used in combination with the EU logo in accordance with the EU guidelines.

The following figure shows the approach taken by the graphic designer and the synthesis process when developing the logo and the final full-colour project logo:

VISUAL IDENTITY

Synthesis Process

Imagotype

The proposal is based on the mussels, the key product to save the marine ecosystem and boost a sustainable economic resource.

The versions were developed from the reduction of shapes, differentiated from one another by their degree of abstraction.

The idea was to push the representation to the limit to play with the figure of the mussel as a synthetic element, in a striking, almost decorative way.

Core Color Palette

Figure 3 Visual identity

Figure 4 Full colour project logo

Besides the colour version, the logo can also be used in monochrome versions depending on the background of the communication material:

Figure 5 Monochrome project logo

Main typeface

INTER-BOLD
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890!@#\$%^&()*=?_;

Modification Examples

Imagotype typeface

The Baltic MUPPETS proposals were created from the Inter typeface family, in its variable bold. This typography was taken as a base and then its forms were adjusted according to the nature of the referent elements and the identity message.

Complementary typeface

As a complementary font, the Roboto typography was chosen in its different variants to be applied in the different digital and printed graphic pieces.

Only the main variables are shown here. You can download the complete family font from Google Fonts at the link below:

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Roboto?query=roboto>

Complementary typeface

Roboto Regular
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Roboto Regular Italic
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Roboto Bold
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Roboto Bold Italic
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Roboto Light
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Roboto Light Italic
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Roboto Black
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Roboto Black Italic
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Figure 6 Typography

The picture below shows the possible logo and visual identity applications for communication material such as project flyers, websites and roll-up, among others.

Figure 7 Examples of communication material

Additionally, other graphical elements have been developed by the graphic designer to visualise the focus of the project on developing high-quality pet food. For additional branding of the project, the following silhouettes of a cat and dog can be used:

Figure 8 Additional graphical elements

The use of the logo and graphical elements will be detailed in visual identity guidelines and templates that will be available for all project partners.

REFERENCES

1: H2020 Programme Guidance– Social media guide for EU-funded R&I projects

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

2: Quick guide and tools for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

3: Guidebook for socio-economic impact assessment of research infrastructures

https://ri-paths-tool.eu/files/RI-PATHS_Guidebook.pdf

